

Diabetes Mellitus: Pathophysiology, Classification, Complications, and Therapeutic Approaches

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ABSTRACT

Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disorder with abnormally high blood glucose levels that are mainly classified into type 1, type 2 and gestational diabetes. The present study aimed to evaluate the type 1 and type 2 diabetes and special focus on the disease Pathophysiology, Classification, Complications, and Therapeutic Approaches. This review helps to understand the importance of different types of herbal medications, oral hypoglycemic agents, and low dose radiations that are used for the treatment of diabetes mellitus. Traditionally, a variety of medical plants have been used to treat diabetes mellitus, among the most commonly used plants are *Momordica charantia*, and *Carica papaya*. These plants have anti diabetic qualities i.e., to increase insulin secretion, improve glucose uptake, and inhibit glucose absorption. In the recent years, many new classes of oral hypoglycemic agents are used the treatment for both type1 and type2 diabetes, such as (DPP-4) inhibitors, (SGLT2) inhibitors and GLP-1

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receptors. These agents works through various mechanisms that improve glyceimic control, which includes insulin secretion, improving insulin sensitivity, reducing hepatic glucose production, and increases glucose uptake in peripheral tissues. Various low dose radiations are also used for the treatment of diabetes mellitus that includes LIL or LLP), which have therapeutic effect on skin wound healing in diabetic patients. Certain other therapies like newer insulin, insulin delivery devices, islet cell transplantation, stem cell technology, artificial pancreas systems were made for glucose management. Some conventional therapeutic approaches like exercise and weight control, medical nutrient therapy, oral glucose drugs, insulin injections are made for the control of diabetes.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, Gestational Diabetes, *Momordica Charantia*, DPP-4 Inhibitors, Hypoglycemic Agents.

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a complex and non-transmissible endocrine disease that has become a global clinical problem. Insulin is released from beta cells in the pancreas to remove glucose from the blood, allowing it to be absorbed and metabolized by muscle and liver [1]. But when there is disturbance or resistance in the secretion of insulin from the beta cells then it gives rise to a metabolic disorder which is commonly known as diabetes mellitus.

Increase the glucose and cholesterol levels in the blood, combined with oxidative stress, can lead to chronic issues affecting various organs such as the kidneys, eyes, nerves, and blood vessels. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), diabetes is a deadly outbreak that causes widespread illness. This condition affects around 387 million people worldwide and is expected to reach over 640 million by 2040 [2]. Diabetes is a leading cause of death worldwide, posing a significant risk to humanity. Approximately 387 million individuals worldwide are affected by the condition, with an 8.3% prevalence rate and 46.3% remaining undiagnosed [3]. China has the highest number of diabetes cases (98.4 million), followed by India with 65.1 million [4]. Asian Indians have a higher risk of diabetes and coronary artery disease due to factors such as insulin resistance [5-7]. Choosing and implementing a glucose-lowering therapy depends on factors such as hyperglycemia severity, hepatic and renal function, hypoglycemia risks, body mass index, self-monitoring ability, and medication cost [8]. In 2017, the International Diabetes Federation (IDF) reported that 425 million people have diabetes mellitus, with over 90% being adults. Additionally, 352 million have impaired glucose tolerance (IGT) [9]. According to the International Diabetes Federation, in 2021, the global prevalence of DM in the adult population was approximately 10.5% (537 million), and this number is expected to increase to 643 million by 2030 [10].

Diabetes prevalence has continuing to rise sharply on a global scale. As of 2011, 366 million individuals worldwide were estimated to have DM, with type 2 accounting for almost 90% of cases [11-12]. Type 2 diabetes is becoming more prevalent worldwide, with 80% of those who have the disease residing in low- and middle-income nations. Research on the prevalence of type 2 diabetes in Africa as a whole has revealed a dearth of information. Research looking at data patterns in Africa shows that

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prevalence has dramatically increased in both rural and urban areas, affecting both genders proportionately [13]. The 2008 World Fact Book report states that the prevalence of diabetes mellitus in Africa was 3.2%, with 40,895 persons (2.0) was in Ethiopia [14]. The World Health Organization (WHO) states that the number of people with diabetes has increased from 108 million in 1980 to 422 million in 2014. The prevalence of this disease continues to increase rapidly in low and less income countries, are not behaving in the same way in the high income countries [15-16]. It was estimated that in 2019 the disease was the main cause of 1.5 million deaths and in 2012, 2.2 million people died because of diabetes. This study will cover the various types of diabetes, their classification, complications, and current treatments to alleviate symptoms and cure diabetes.

Types of Diabetes

Type 1 diabetes

In type 1 diabetes, the autoimmune destruction of beta cells results in a nearly complete lack of insulin production. As a result, glucose accumulates in the bloodstream, leading to hyperglycemia [17]. In contrast, type 2 diabetes is marked by insulin resistance, which arises when body cells become less responsive to insulin's glucose-lowering effects [18]. This causes a compensatory increase in insulin production, but eventually the pancreas is unable to keep up with the demand, leading in hyperglycemia. Insulin resistance is frequently accompanied by poor insulin secretion, worsening the metabolic abnormalities. The pathophysiology of diabetes includes the action of glucagon, a pancreatic hormone that elevates blood glucose levels. Diabetes frequently results in high glucagon levels, which contribute to hyperglycemia [19].

Type I diabetes causes decreased insulin secretion due to autoantibodies destroying pancreatic β -cells. This leads to hyperglycemia and acidosis from low blood insulin levels. Pancreatic β -cells are destroyed when the immune system loses tolerance and attacks them as alien. T cells govern this process. Identifying and modifying the pathways that lead to β -cell assault by specific antibodies and immune cells can prevent the establishment of diabetes [20]. Immune cells have been linked to type I diabetes in patients with particular HLA system antigens and high blood sugar levels. Research on the human genome found HLA class II as a hereditary risk factor for type I diabetes, accounting for 50% of cases. This shows that the immune system's presentation of a specific peptide plays a role in the disease's development [21]. Type I diabetes is typically associated with a polygenic syndrome, however it can also occur in isolated cases. For example, the Autoimmune Regulator gene is linked to autoimmune poly glandular syndrome type 1 [22]. Autoimmunity can be indicated by the presence of antibodies against insulin, glutamate decarboxylase, insulinoma antigen 2, or zinc transporter 8 in the patient's plasma, which can be measured and correlated with disease severity. CD4+ and CD8+ T cells, found in peripheral blood, pancreatic tissue, and per pancreatic lymph nodes, may influence the synthesis of autoantibodies. However, in patients with type I diabetes, these cells have activity against β cells [23-24]. The presence of auto reactive species in peripheral blood is low, comparable to healthy individuals, the only CD 8+ cells exhibit abnormal activity in the periphery due to activation-related changes (25). These CD8+ cells

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exhibit unique functional characteristics, including low epitope affinity for HLA complexes and minimal interaction with antigen-presenting cells. T receptor alterations that interact with the HLA-epitope complex may not trigger a widespread immune response. These issues stem from inadequate thymic maturation during development [26-28].

Type 2 diabetes

The pathophysiology of type 2 diabetes mellitus is distinguished by insulin deficiency and insulin resistance, which have been linked to inflammatory cytokines in the plasma and high fatty acid levels, resulting in insufficient glucose transport into target cells, increased fat breakdown, and increased hepatic glucose production [29]. Hyperglycemia results from excessive glucagon secretion and insulin insufficiency by the glucagon-secreting alpha cell and the insulin-secreting beta cell, respectively. Type 2 diabetes mellitus is diagnosed when patients are unable to increase insulin secretion to compensate for insulin resistance, resulting in an elevated glycemic value [30]. One of the main reasons of this occurrence is β -cell malfunction, which results in insufficient secretion compared to the necessity to maintain a stable glucose level. Insulin resistance occurs when certain receptors are unable to respond to stimuli, resulting in increased glucose production in the liver but decreased utilization in muscle and adipose tissue [31]. Insulin is synthesized in pancreatic β cells by structural modifications of pro-insulin and stored in vesicles for secretion when needed. Glucose stimulates its release from blood cells through the glucose transporter, a cation transport protein that alters the ATP/ADP ratio and closes potassium channels. This causes an increase in ATP concentration and intracellular calcium buildup, causing insulin granules to migrate to the cell membrane and be removed through exocytosis [32].

If Excessive food consumption can cause chronic inflammation and damage to pancreatic islet tissue, including oxidative, amyloid, and metabolic stress [33]. Obesity and metabolic stress can trigger lipotoxicity, glucotoxicity, and glycoprotein toxicity by activating the cellular apoptotic unfolded protein response (UPR) at the β -cell level [34]. Increased fatty acid levels can block the sarcoplasmic reticulum, leading to decreased intracellular calcium mobilization. Persistent diabetes can cause β -cells to produce more proinsulin and islet amyloid polypeptides (IAAPs), resulting in proinsulin misfolding in three dimensions. As it accumulates in the cytoplasm, it causes oxidative stress, resulting in tissue damage and persistent inflammation [35].

Another con Hyperglycemia and glucotoxicity can cause an increase in reactive oxygen species (ROS), leading to inflammation and oxidative stress. Excess ROS inactivated mitochondria, rendering them incapable of metabolizing superoxide ions. They play a direct role in diabetes pathogenesis, leading to the formation of advanced glycation end products (AGEs) through the polyol pathway. Thus, a series of changes occur and Normal cell physiology changes, such as increased expression of AGE receptors and activation of protein kinase C isoforms [36-37].

Reduced Physical activity increases the risk of obesity and type II diabetes. Metabolic inflammation, characterized by the production of cytokines such IL-6, TNF α , and IL-1 into the bloodstream, can occur to varying degrees [38].

Elevated IL-1 levels cause pancreatic β -cells to produce NF-KB, leading to decreased

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insulin release and death. Losing weight can increase insulin sensitivity, improve glycemic control, and lower cardiovascular risk. The mechanism for this is the release of anti-inflammatory cytokines like IL-1 and TNF- α . Antioxidants, including glutathione, can neutralize free radicals caused by abnormal metabolic pathways [39-41].

Gestational diabetes

Gestational diabetes mellitus is the type of diabetes that occurs during pregnancy. The changes in hormones level can lead to insulin resistance, reducing the body's ability to respond to insulin [42]. Those women who have developed diabetes during pregnancy and those women who are diagnosed with unrecognized, asymptomatic type 2 diabetes during pregnancy are both classified as having gestational diabetes [43]. Gestational diabetes is associated with significant maternal and intrauterine fetal death or stillbirth, including fetal neonatal hypoglycemia, fetal macrosomia and it increases the risk of delivery complications such as birth trauma, shoulder dystocia and C-section delivery [44-45]. Women with gestational diabetes have a high rate of chance to develop diabetes type 2 later in life, with 30-60% of women diagnosed with type 2 diabetes within 20 years after the delivery [46-47]. Pregnancy-related glucose intolerance can cause hyperglycemia of varying severity [48]. GDM, or impaired glucose intolerance, affects 14% of pregnant women or 135,000 women annually in the United States. It is a risk factor for type 2 diabetes in mothers [49-50]. The reported risk of GDM and type 2 diabetes varies by ethnicity, selection criteria, and testing [51]. To reduce maternal and fetal problems, recent guidelines suggest maintaining sufficient glycemic management. Most women with gestational diabetes can manage their blood sugar via diet and exercise, but some may require oral diabetes medication or insulin.

Classification of diabetes

Insulin dependent diabetes (IDDM)

Diabetes or juvenile onset or type 1, affects 5-10% of patients and is caused by autoimmune destruction of pancreatic cells. The condition can affect individuals of various ages, but typically affects children and young adults. Regular insulin injections are necessary to maintain blood glucose levels under control. The rate of β cell breakdown varies, with newborns and children experiencing faster deterioration than adults. Ketoacidosis symptoms are common in children and young adults, although mild fasting hyperglycemia can progress to severe hyperglycemia or ketoacidosis in response to stress or infection [52]. These patients are more likely to develop other autoimmune disorders, such as Graves' disease, vitiligo, coeliac spur, autoimmune hepatitis, myasthenia gravis, Hashimoto's thyroiditis, Addison's disease, and pernicious anemia [52].

Idiopathic Diabetes

A small percentage of patients with type 1 diabetes, primarily of Asian and African descent, have no known cause. These are susceptible to ketoacidosis and have persistent insulin deficiency. Ketoacidosis occurs in episodes, with fluctuating insulin shortage levels. Idiopathic diabetes is genetically predisposed and requires insulin

replacement therapy based on the patient's condition [52].

Noninsulin dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM)

Adult-onset diabetes makes up 90-95% of all diabetes cases. Obesity, insulin resistance, and dyslipidemia are major metabolic disorders that contribute to the epidemic of type 2 diabetes [53]. This kind of diabetes is treated with oral hypoglycemic medications, which are dietary. Insulin resistance and decreased insulin production lead to disease development. Type 2 diabetes is the fourth greatest cause of death in developed nations, with a twofold increase in mortality and a fourfold increase in the risk of coronary heart disease and stroke [54].

Catamenial Hyperglycemia

Diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA) can be caused by infection, low insulin, poor insulin compliance, severe pancreatitis, stroke, medications, metabolic changes, or treatment neglect [55]. Catamenial diabetic ketoacidosis or Catamenial hyperglycemia refers to uncontrolled hyperglycemia in females that occurs before their menstrual cycle. Uncontrolled hyperglycemia required up to four times more insulin. The situation worsens even with continuous insulin infusion, causing vomiting, acidosis, ketonuria, and hyperglycemia. Several tests, including inflammatory indicators, blood count, renal function, ECG, chest radiograph, thyroid function, and urine/blood cultures, were normal.

Pathophysiology of diabetes mellitus

Diabetes is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by hyperglycemia, which causes significantly elevated blood sugar levels. Hyperglycemia can be produced by insulin production, action, or a combination of both, leading to long-term dysfunctions in carbohydrate, protein, and lipid metabolism [56]. Long-term effects of diabetes include diabetic retinopathy (risk of blindness), nephropathy (kidney failure), and neuropathy (foot ulcers, Charcot's joints, and amputations), autonomic neuropathy (which causes gastrointestinal issues), sexual dysfunction, and cardiovascular abnormalities. Individuals with DM frequently have hypertension and poor lipoprotein metabolism. As a result, they are more prone to peripheral arterial, cerebrovascular, cardiovascular, and atherosclerosis diseases [52]. T1DM causes the autoimmune destruction of insulin-producing cells in the pancreas. The immune system's CD4+ and CD8+ T cells destroy these cells, while macrophages harm the pancreatic islets. T1DM is characterized by insufficient insulin secretion due to autoimmune death of pancreatic β -cells, which can cause metabolic problems [57]. In type 2 diabetes, the processes that maintain normal physiological glucose levels breakdown causes two key pathophysiological defects: decreased insulin secretion due to pancreatic β -cell malfunction and impaired insulin action due to IR [58]. Diabetes significantly increases the risk of CVD diseases such as CAD, stroke, atrial fibrillation, and heart failure. CVD remains the leading cause of death among diabetics [59]. Understanding the complex pathophysiology of diabetes is crucial for managing its effects.

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Pathophysiology Type 1 diabetes mellitus

T1DM is a genetic immune system disorder affecting individuals of all ages, including preadolescents, young adults, and the elderly. T1DM develops due to the loss of pancreatic β cells, which is largely caused by T-lymphocytes [60]. Insulinitis occurs when immune cells invade pancreatic islets, causing inflammation. Islet infiltration is likely caused by β -cells, as insulinitis is only found in β -cell islets [61]. T-cells cause inflammation and destroy β cells in islets [61]. Specific genes can impair the immune system's ability to distinguish between self and others.

Autoimmune disorders, such as T1DM, can result from non-self-interactions [60]. The genes linked to T1DM are known as human leucocyte antigens (HLA) and belong to the MHC region. HLA complex polymorphism alleles account for 40-50% of the hereditary risk of T1DM. HLA gene loci are classified as Class I and Class II. T1DM-associated HLA alleles are Class II and play a significant role in antigen presentation to T helper cells. Substitutions in the peptide-binding areas of Class II alleles can change the binding affinity for auto antigens, either reducing or increasing the autoimmune response. Several investigations have found alterations in the makeup of leukocytes linked with T1DM.

These comprise NKT cells, dendritic cells, CD45R-subpopulations, CD4 and CD8 T-cells. However, the causes and effects on disease progression are still being investigated [61]. Insulin insufficiency can cause major effects on protein, carbohydrate, and lipid metabolism. Insulin shortage disrupts glucose metabolism, causing metabolic diseases such as glycosuria, polydipsia, and polyphagia. Uncontrolled T1DM leads to high levels of free fatty acids (FFA) in the plasma due to rapid triglyceride mobilization. Insulin insufficiency causes hypertriglyceridemia and increases the risk of proteolysis, raising plasma amino acid concentrations. Additionally, hyperglycemia in T1DM is exacerbated by hepatic and renal gluconeogenesis of glycogenic amino acids [58].

Pathophysiology Type 2 diabetes mellitus

T2DM causes elevated plasma glucose levels due to impaired insulin production and action [62]. Understanding the etiology of this multifactorial disease has proven challenging. However, T2DM can be categorized as a hereditary disorder. Various genes regulate insulin secretion, action, and β -cell activity. These genes are vital for producing enzymes. Genetic impairments can lead to a series of metabolic reactions, including insulin resistance, increased liver glucose production, impaired fatty acid and glucose uptake, and increased TG breakdown. [60].

Insulin secretion degradation, including hyperglycemia and lipo-toxicity, can lead to a decrease in β -cell mass if not addressed, as shown in animal studies. The progression worsens the long-term regulation of blood glucose levels [63]. Glucolipotoxicity and amyloid accumulation lead to β -cell death through oxidative and endoplasmic reticulum stress [64].

Other organs have an important part in the pathogenesis of Type 2 Diabetes [62]. The liver produces excess glucose due to insulin resistance, higher glucagon levels, and enhanced glucagon sensitivity. Furthermore, insulin is capable of crossing the blood brain barrier (BBB) suppresses hunger by modulating neuropeptides that control food intake. Excess FFAs can cause adipocytes to resist insulin's anti-lipolytic impact.

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Chronic high levels of FFAs disrupt metabolism, leading to gluconeogenesis, IR in skeletal muscle and liver, and decreased insulin secretion [65]. Nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), which is often linked to T2DM, causes an increase in FFA buildup in the liver due to insulin resistance. This accumulation not only worsens NAFLD by causing chronic liver cell stress, but also sets off a cycle of increased lipid accumulation. Obesity, a risk factor for T2DM, lowers adiponectin levels, which normally suppress proinflammatory cytokines. Examples include TNF- α and IL-6. Reduced adiponectin levels promote cytokine production, causing inflammation in adipocytes and increasing insulin resistance [66]. Obesity-induced inflammation is linked to IR via the IKK β /NF-KB pathway. Diabetes management recommendations urge a minimum 5% weight decrease for overweight and obese patients. To effectively manage diabetes, a personalized diet, increased physical activity, and behavioral therapy are recommended [67].

Metabolic pathways and complications

Hyperglycemia causes tissue damage via multiple interrelated metabolic mechanisms. These include the polyol pathway, hexamine biosynthetic pathway, activation of protein kinase C, and increased development of advanced glycation end-products (AGEs). The polyol pathway converts excess glucose to sorbitol and then fructose, depleting NADPH and glutathione and increasing oxidative stress. The hexamine route converts excess glucose into N-acetylglucosamine, which influences transcription factors and gene expression. Protein kinase C activation impacts vascular permeability and blood flow. AGEs crosslink proteins, disrupting normal function and causing inflammation. These pathways produce reactive oxygen species, leading to a cycle of oxidative stress that can cause tissue damage even after hyperglycemia is under control [68].

Diabetic retinopathy

Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is a prevalent condition that affects the blood vessels of the retina, affecting 93 million people globally [69]. The condition is typically diagnosed 5 years after symptoms appear and, if untreated, can result in vision loss [70]. Hyperglycemia causes long-term damage to retinal capillaries, leading to endothelial dysfunction, including microangiopathy and arterial stiffness. There are two stages of diabetic retinopathy: non-proliferative (NPDR) and proliferative (PDR). NPDR is an early stage of DR marked by increased vascular permeability, balloon-like capillaries in the retina, and disruption of the blood-retinal barrier (BRB). PDR is the advanced stage where new blood vessels form to compensate for swollen capillaries that cannot bring blood to all retinal cells. Breaking these new arteries can lead to vitreous haemorrhage and retinal detachment, resulting in visual loss [71]. Diabetes management is the primary treatment for DR, however advanced cases may require laser therapy or surgery [71].

Diabetic neuropathy

Diabetic neuropathy is one of the most devastating consequences of diabetes mellitus, which can cause death. Hyperglycemia can cause neuronal damage, affecting numerous. The polyol and hexamine pathways in neurons [72]. In example, peripheral

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neuropathy affects 30-50% of diabetics and is typically classed as multifocal neuropathy. Symptoms include leg discomfort and numbness. Arms are affected as a result of autonomic small fiber injury. It is commonly detected by thermal threshold testing measures a person's sensitivity to temperature fluctuations. Patients with DN typically have a decreased ability to sense those changes [73-74]. A useful technique for identifying patients with peripheral neuropathy is the neuropath test assesses plantar sweat production. Abnormal results may indicate sudomotor dysfunction linked to peripheral neuropathy [74]. Early diagnosis of DN is useful to immediately start treatment and prevent damage of the large nerve fibers that can be deadly.

Diabetic Nephropathy

Diabetic nephropathy is another common type 1 and type 2 diabetes complication. This condition causes kidney function loss and contributes to CKD and ESRD [75]. Diabetic nephropathy is classified into four stages based on the severity of vascular, interstitial, and glomerular abnormalities. Diabetic nephropathy is typically treated with anti-diabetic medications. It is linked to an increased risk of death, especially from cardiovascular disease.

Diabetic Ketoacidosis

Although it is more frequently linked to type 1 diabetes, diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA) can happen to any diabetic patient when their body is under a lot of stress. "A lack of insulin can cause harmful substances called ketones to build up in the blood," according to clinical resources. Increased lipolysis and cytogenesis result from the pathophysiology of insulin insufficiency coupled with high levels of counter-regulatory hormones (glucagon, catecholamines, cortisol, and growth hormone). When paired with fluid losses from osmotic diuresis, the ensuing metabolic acidosis poses a serious risk to life and necessitates prompt medical attention. Polyuria, polydipsia, nausea, vomiting, stomach pain, and in extreme situations, Kussmaul respirations and altered mental status are among the clinical symptoms [76].

Macro Vascular Complications

Diabetes has several macro vascular complications [77]. Diabetes mellitus is an independent risk factor for heart failure, making it a prevalent consequence. The Framingham study found that diabetes increases the risk of heart failure by two times in men and five times in women compared to non-diabetics [78]. Diabetes complications are 30-40% more common in people with heart failure [79], indicating a strong link between the two conditions. Diabetes and heart failure are linked to metabolic illnesses such glucose toxicity and lipotoxicity, as well as complications from ischemic heart disease. The diagnosis is based on insulin resistance, vascular endothelial dysfunction, microcirculation disease, and capillary failure. Several mechanisms are involved. Diabetic cardiomyopathy refers to cardiac dysfunction that occurs without severe coronary artery disease, hypertension, or valvular heart disease [80-83]. However, its existence has been contested for years [84-85]. The 2013 ACC/AHA Heart Failure Guidelines provide information on diabetic cardiomyopathy [86].

Online ISSN

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Cardiovascular disease

Diabetes has resulted in the deaths of 1.6 million people, primarily from cardiovascular disorders [87]. Diabetes patients with no myocardial infarction are equally likely to develop acute coronary syndrome as nondiabetics with myocardial infarction. Diabetes individuals have twice the death rate following myocardial infarction compared to non-diabetic patients [88]. Diabetes patients are at risk for cardiovascular disease due to insulin resistance, hyperglycemia, and excess free fatty acids. These factors increase oxidative stress and disrupt PKC signaling, leading to vascular swelling, constriction, thrombosis, and atherogenesis [88]. Hypoglycemia is linked to higher risk.

Cerebrovascular disease

Diabetes increases the likelihood of developing cerebrovascular disorders, with 20% of diabetics dying from stroke [89-90]. The study examined the relationship between HbA1c, fasting glucose levels, insulin resistance, and beta cell function with various types of cerebrovascular diseases. High HbA1c levels, insulin resistance, and beta cell dysfunction raise the risk of big and small artery ischaemic strokes. Hb1Ac levels are linked to carotid atherosclerosis, fractional anisotropy, and white matter and brain atrophy markers, indicating a link between diabetes and cerebrovascular disease [91].

Peripheral artery disease

Peripheral artery disease (PAD) causes reduced blood flow to the extremities due to atherosclerosis and plaque formation in vessel walls [92]. Diabetes induces vascular dysfunction, inflammation, and atherosclerotic plaque deposition in the arteries, making PAD more frequent in diabetics than non-diabetics [93]. Patients with PAD and diabetes are more likely to develop foot ulcers and require lower extremity amputations [94]. Minority populations, including Native Americans, African Americans, and rural inhabitants, have been found to be at increased risk of lower extremities amputation compared with whites, suggesting that a difficult socioeconomic environment influences the availability of appropriate health care tools favoring drastic and irreversible medical interventions, such as leg amputation [95].

Therapeutic approaches

Therapeutic approaches towards cardiovascular diseases (CVD)

Macro albuminuria and micro albuminuria are strongly associated with a heightened risk of cardiovascular disease (CVD) [96]. According to the MICRO-HOPE trial, the use of ramipril, an ACE inhibitor, notably reduces the chances of diabetic nephropathy, stroke, death due to cardiovascular causes, need for revascularization procedures, and overall mortality. Similarly, findings from the LIFE study revealed that losartan, an angiotensin receptor blocker (ARB), significantly lowers the risk of cardiovascular death, stroke, and myocardial infarction (MI). The risk of cardiovascular-related death or hospitalization due to heart failure was reduced by 23% [97].

Online ISSN

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Pharmacological approaches to reduce cardio metabolic risk in obese diabetic patients

Obesity greatly contributes to increased mortality and health complications in individuals with both diabetes mellitus (DM) and cardiovascular disease (CVD) [98]. People with diabetes often have a broader waist circumference compared to non-diabetics [99]. In addition to the heart-protective benefits of traditional oral hypoglycemic agents (OHAs) like metformin and TZDs[100], newer treatments such as GLP-1 receptor agonists and SGLT-2 inhibitors are showing encouraging results in managing cardiovascular risks in obese diabetic patients[101-102]. The Diabetes Prevention Study emphasized the role of weight reduction in decreasing the risk of CVD events. Both GLP-1 and SGLT-2 agents contribute to weight loss, further proving their effectiveness in lowering CVD-related mortality [103]. A meta-analysis confirmed that SGLT2 notably reduced the likelihood of such events [104-105]. Additionally, GLP-1 significantly decreased the occurrence of cardiovascular complications and deaths by 10% and 13%, respectively, among patients with type 2 diabetes (T2DM) [106].

Therapeutic strategies for managing hypertension

High blood pressure is a key contributor to the widespread occurrence of cardiovascular diseases (CVDs), which are a leading cause of death in individuals with diabetes. Medications such as ACE inhibitors have been shown to lower the risk of hypertensive individuals developing diabetes by 11–34% [107-108], emphasizing their crucial role in reducing CVD among diabetic patients. The Hypertension Optimal Treatment (HOT) trial suggests keeping diastolic blood pressure (DBP) under 85 mm Hg, which may help in decreasing CVD risk [171]. In diabetic patients, β -blockers have shown positive outcomes [109-110], particularly atenolol, which significantly reduces complications and death from CVD, as confirmed by the UKPDS study [111]. Moreover, the calcium channel blocker fenoldopam, used as a first-line therapy in the HOT trial, was found effective in minimizing CVD events by controlling DBP in diabetic individuals [112].

Strategies for treating hyperlipidemia (Dyslipidemia)

Targeting dyslipidemia is expected to notably decrease the occurrence of issues like CVD among diabetics, as it is a major risk factor [113]. Dyslipidemia in diabetes is typically marked by elevated triglycerides, lower HDL levels, and a higher concentration of LDL particles. These lipid abnormalities play a key role in CVD development [114-115].

Herbal plants that are used for treatment of diabetes mellitus:

Momordica Charantia

It is a member of the Cucurbitaceae family and is frequently referred to as bitter melon (karela). *Momordica 1* and *Momordica 2*, as well as cucurbitacin B, are the active ingredients of *Momordica charantia*. It is employed to treat diabetes. It contains lectin, which functions similarly to insulin. A nonprotein called lectin is connected to insulin receptors. By affecting peripheral tissues, this lectin lowers blood sugar level [116]. *M. charantia* fruit extract has hypoglycemic action at 200mg/kg.

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Carica papaya

The papaya, a member of the Caricaceae family, has been shown to lower blood sugar levels, reduce body lipids, and promote wound healing in alloxan induced diabetic rats when its seeds and leaves are extracted [117].

Allium sativum

Allium sativum is known locally as garlic since it is a member of the Liliaceae family, which includes Allium sativum. Garlic ethanol extract (10 ml/kg/day) frequently exhibits hypoglycemic effects [118]. Garlic extract outperformed the antidiabetic medication glibenclamide. In rats given STZ, ethanol, petroleum ether extract, and ethyl acetate few found to exhibit anti diabetic effects. Garlic has a number of medicinal benefit, including antimicrobia, antiplatelet, blood pressure, and cholesterol reduction [118].

Aloe borbadensis

Borbadensis aloe it is a member of the Liliaceae family and is called Ghikanvar. With its green blade – shaped, heavily narrowing, hairy leaves that are packed with clear viscid gel, it resembles a cactus plant. Blood glucose levels are considerably reduced when aloe vera aqueous extract is taken orally at a dose of 150 mg/kg of body weight [119]. Aloe vera gel has several medicinal benefits, including anti – diabetic and antioxidant properties. It also quadruples levels in diabetic rats [120].

Mangifera indica:

It belongs to the Anacardiaceae family and is frequently referred to as a mango. In rats with alloxan – induced diabetes, oral treatment of an aqueous extract did not alter blood glucose levels, whereas leaves extract (250 mg/kg) demonstrated anti – diabetic action [121].

Eugenia jambolana

It is a member of the Myrtaceae family and is called jamun. It has mature Eugenia jambolana fruits and dry seeds. Ferulic acid and malvidin 3-laminaribioside are its active constituents. Patients with diabetes are treated with a dried seed extract (200 mg/kg) [122].

Effects of chemicals on diabetes mellitus:

DDP-4 inhibitors

DDP-4 inhibitors, such as saxagliptin and sitagliptin, function by preventing the breakdown of GLP-1 by the enzyme DDP-4. GLP-1 is raised as a result, which promotes the release of insulin and inhibits the release of glucagon [123].

SGLT2 inhibitors

SGLT2 inhibitors, including canagliflozin and dapagliflozin, enhance the excretion of glucose in the urine by preventing the kidneys from reabsorbing glucose [124].

GLP-1 receptor

Exenatide are examples of GLP-1 receptor agonists that function by imitating GLP-1s

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actions and promoting the release of glucagon and insulin [125].

Thiazolidindion

For the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus, thiazolidindion, commonly referred to as glitazones, are regarded as a well – established class of anti – diabetic drugs and a physiologically active scaffold. By increasing peripheral glucose synthesis and disposal, thiazolidinediones lower insulin resistance. These compounds activate one of subtype of PPARs, the peroxisome proliferated activated receptor (PPAR γ). A variety of its hybrids have also demonstrated antidiabetic and other therapeutic properties [126].

Sulfonylureas

Due to its rising frequency and debilitating effects, diabetes mellitus (DM) is a rapidly expanding epidemic and a global public health concern. Oral glucose-lowering medications known as sulfonylureas (SUs) are used as second line treatments for type 2 diabetes (T2D) because of their effective glycaemic control, and renal advantages. Despite certain adverse effects, SUs immediately insulin production by the pancreas. It plays a role in the onset and advancement of hypoglycemia. It is used in place of or in addition to metformin. Elderly weak people who are at increased risk of hypoglycemia. It is used in place of or in addition to metformin. Elderly weak people who are at increased risk of hypoglycemia should avoid SUs [127].

Biguanides

Because of their positive safety profiles and ability to decrease blood sugar, biguanides, like metformin, have long been considered the first choice drugs for the treatment of type 2 diabetes. However, there has been a lot of discussion and investigation due to worries about the possibility of lactic acidosis linked to biguanide use. The goal of this study is to present a thorough examination of the connection between lactic acidosis and biguanides, specifically metformin. We examine the fundamental processes, epidemiological data, risk factors, clinical presentations, diagnostic issues, and treatment approaches associated with lactic acidosis brought on by biguanides. We also examine current research findings, debates, and potential paths forward in this crucial field of clinical practice and pharmacovigilance [128].

Radiation on diabetes mellitus

There is sample evidence that low-dose radiation (LDR) can induce hormesis and adaptive response. LDR-induced adaptive response was cross-resistance to other non-radiation stressors, like chemicals, in addition to being resistant to damage from a subsequent high-dose radiation. Induced or up-regulated production of defensive proteins, including as heart shock proteins and antioxidants, is one mechanism by which LDR produces the protective effect against tissue damage caused by radiation or chemicals.

This review will provide an overview of the available data, with a focus on the preventive effect of LDR on the development of diabetes and the therapeutic effect of LDR on diabetic cardiovascular complications, as oxidative damage to tissues is a major pathogenesis of many human diseases including diabetes. According to the

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information provided, pre-exposure of mice to LDR delayed the onset of hyperglycemia in diabetes-prone non-obese diabetic mice and decreased the incidence of alloxan-induced diabetes. Low-intensity or power laser (LIL or LPL) radiation has been in animals experiments to have a therapeutic effect on skin wound healing. This has led to the clinical use of LIL to treat diabetes patient's skin ulcers.

Although the exact mechanisms by which LDR prevents diabetes are unknown, they may involve immunomodulation to maintain pancreatic antioxidants to shield cells from oxidative damage. The mechanisms underlying LIL's therapeutic effect on diabetic wound healing may include immunomodulation, beta cell proliferation stimulation, antioxidant action, and enhancement of systemic and wound regional microcirculation. Therefore, numerous research have shown that LDR, specifically LIL, is a therapeutically effective treatment for diabetic wound healing, even though there are only a handful that show LDR prevents the development of diabetes. These early findings are very motivating for us to investigate the clinical implications of LDR in areas connected to diabetes [128].

Emerging trends

Improving glycaemic control, lowering complications, and improving patient quality of life are the driving forces behind emerging trends in diabetes management

Incretin mimetics

Insulin mimetic are drugs, which include GLP-1 analogues, increases the secretion of insulin, prevent the release of glucagon, and postpone the emptying of the stomach [128].

Dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) Inhibitors

Medications such as saxagliptin and sitagliptin prevent GLP-1 from being broken down, which raises insulin output and leaves glucagon levels [128].

Sodium glucose cotransporter 2 (SGLT2) inhibitors

Drugs like canagliflozin and dapagliflozin increases glucose excretion and improve glycaemic management by decreasing the kidney ability to reabsorb glucose [128].

Newer insulins

Insulin glargine, detemir, and degludec are examples of long acting insulins that offer more consistent and long lasting glucose management [128].

Insulin delivery devices

Insulin administration and glucose control have been enhanced by developments in insulin pens, jets, and continuous subcutaneous insulin infusion pumps [128].

Islet cell transplantation

To restore insulin production, donor beta cells are transplanted into the host's portal vein in this promising treatment [128].

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3007-3197

Print ISSN

3007-3189

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Stem cell technology

The ability of stem cells to enhance insulin action and regenerate beta cells is being investigated by researchers [128].

Artificial pancreas systems

Systems of artificial pancreas by combining continuous glucose monitoring with insulin delivery, these systems seek automate glucose management [128].

Conventional therapeutic approaches for diabetes management

Exercise and weight control

It has been demonstrated that exercise helps patients with glycemic blood levels [129-130] found that aerobic, resistance, and combined training methods are effective in lowering HbA1c levels. They also found that a diet high in proteins, low in carbohydrates, and low in glycemic index (similar to the Mediterranean diet) lowers blood sugar levels in diabetic patients who are at high risk of cardiovascular disease [129-130]. In 50% of patients with long-duration type 2 diabetes, this regimen is more effective than all antidiabetic treatments at achieving non-diabetic fasting glucose levels [131]. Diabetes remission is linked to intensive weight loss interventions based on physical activity, food, and social support [132-133], underscoring the significance of weight control in the treatment of diabetes.

Oral glucose drugs

Biguanides, sulfonylureas, meglitinides, and thiazolidinediones are the primary classes of oral medications used to treat diabetes [134-141]. One of those medications, pioglitazone, a thiazolidinedione, has raised some health issues in a number of studies. It effectively lowers fasting blood glucose and HbA1c levels, but it can also result in edema and an increase in body weight [134]. However, the medication is utilized by those who have cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and dyslipidemia. A lower risk of heart attack, diabetes complications, and death is linked to sulfonylureas and metformin [134-141]. Despite their beneficial medicinal effects, sulfonylureas, such as metformin and glyburide, have been associated with a higher risk of hypoglycemia than pioglitazone [141].

Insulin injections

Patients with type 1 diabetes who are unable to make insulin spontaneously are treated mostly with insulin injections [142]. Patients with type 2 diabetes are less likely to need insulin therapy, and when diet, exercise, weight loss, and oral antidiabetic medications fail to lower blood glucose levels as intended, insulin therapy is employed [143]. After at least two months of dual oral therapy, insulin therapy is initiated when HbA1c levels are above 7%. If this doesn't happen, insulin is gradually administered along with other drugs to guarantee optimal blood glucose control. To reach and maintain HbA1c levels below 7%, several insulin injections must be given daily as one is typically insufficient [144]. The two potential adverse effects of insulin therapy are weight gain and hypoglycemia. For insulin therapy to be effective, patients must restrict their food consumption and check their blood sugar levels at least four times a day, before each meal. Patients with type 1 diabetes can ensure a

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Print ISSN

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long, healthy life if they adhere to this medication, which lowers hypoglycemic and hyperglycemic episodes [145].

Oral glucose drugs

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Future perspective

Combination therapies using peptide hormones

Several hypothalamic-pituitary endocrine axis, which control the activity of the thyroid, pancreatic islets, gonadal and adrenal glands, and other organs, are influenced by the adipocyte-secreted hormone leptin, a protein encoded by the obese (*ob*) genes. Additionally, the hormone has pleiotropic effects on wound healing, osteogenesis, angiogenesis, and the immune system [155-156]. When used to treat a rare form of human obesity brought on by particular *ob* gene mutations, several clinical trials have demonstrated that recombinant human leptin has favorable effects on energy balance and obesity-related endocrinopathies [158]. In addition to its effects on body weight and food intake, leptin possesses strong anti-diabetic properties. Specifically, it can reverse type 1 and type 2 diabetes in animal models. Furthermore, individuals with severe insulin resistance benefit greatly from long-term leptin replacement therapy, which is well tolerated and significantly improves triglyceride levels, insulin sensitivity, and glycemic management [157]. These findings have prompted the development of novel anti-diabetic and anti-obesity therapies that include the use of mimetics, synthetic peptide analogs, and leptin receptor antagonists [157]. Obese mice's glucose and lipid metabolism has improved when those leptin analogs are combined with GLP-1 receptor agonists [156].

Incretins combination therapy

In rodent models of obesity, a new peptide with agonist action at three peptide hormone receptors—GLP-1, glucose dependent insulin tropic polypeptide (GIP), and glucagon receptors—has demonstrated positive effects on body weight and the prevention of diabetic complications [159]. In diabetic animal models, dual co-agonists or best mono-agonists are less effective in reducing body weight, improving glycemic control, or reversing steatosis. Genetic, pharmacological, and selective chemical loss-of-function studies have confirmed the role of each of those molecules in metabolic changes in vivo. A synergistic combination of glucagon, GLP-1, and GIP contributes to the metabolic efficacy of this type of treatment by increasing energy expenditure, decreasing caloric intake, and mitigating the diabetogenic effects of

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glucagon, respectively, improving glucose control [159]. Simultaneously, scientists have created a peptide that strongly co-agonistically interacts with both GLP-1 and GIP receptors, which are Incretin hormones. This unimolecular dual Incretin peptide has a significantly better ant hyperglycemic and insulin tropic effect than other GLP-1 agonists, both in patients with diabetes and in rodent and primate (cynomolgus monkey) models of obesity and diabetes (diabetic (db/db)mice and Zucker diabetic fatty (ZDF)rats). Unlike selective GIP agonists, which have minimal impact on weight loss, dual Incretin co-agonists effectively reduce fat mass in obese rats. Polyethylene Glycol (PEG) ylation, or site-specific limitation, of the proteins results in a longer duration of action and, thus, lower dosage, preventing the negative gastrointestinal effects brought on by the administration of large doses of selective GLP-1 agonists. In any case, more research is required to validate the powerful benefits of dual Incretin agonists in the treatment of type 2 diabetes [160].

Gene therapy

A novel approach to treatment, gene therapy aims to change the patient's genes or cells in order to accomplish the intended outcome. Both in vivo and ex vivo gene therapy are possible. The idea behind ex vivo therapy is to remove the patient's cells from their body, alter their genetic makeup, and then put them back into the patient. Instead, the goal of in vivo therapy is to alter the patient's cells without taking them out of the body.

Ex vivo therapy

The ability of cells other than beta cells to produce insulin has been investigated in some of the earliest research in the field of ex vivo gene therapy, with the aim of implanting these cells in the human body as an extra source of the hormone [161-164]. Rat liver cells, or hepatocytes, were used in those experiments. After being cultured with the insulin promoter factor 1, those cells—which were separated from rodent cells—were able to respond to glucose and sulfonylureas by producing and releasing insulin. These cells were able to lower the no fasting glucose levels in diabetic mice after being transplanted in them [164]. The expression of the pancreatic duodenal home box 1 (Pdx1) gene, a crucial transcription factor in pancreatic development and insulin expression in beta cells, can also elicit the differentiation of fetal human progenitor liver cells (FH) into cells that produce insulin. The ability of those FH cells to respond to glucose by producing and releasing insulin and maintaining euglycemia for extended periods of time in diabetic mice suggests that this method may be a novel source of cells for transplantation into T1DM patients [164]. Cells used in ex vivo gene therapy must be appropriately engineered to respond to glucose in order to prevent episodes of hypoglycemia and hyperglycemia, not trigger the immune response that could result in rejection from the human body, and adjust to physiological changes that occur in the body, such as aging, weight fluctuations, and the body's response to exercise [163].

In Vivo therapy

Since hepatocytes can be made to differentiate into islets and used to replace damaged beta cells in the pancreas, the liver is a target organ for gene therapy. Adenoviruses

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have been employed as vectors to transfer the proinsulin gene into the liver of T1DM-carrying mice as part of an in vivo gene therapy strategy. Upon appropriate stimulation following the infection, those cells were able to produce [165-168]. These findings have demonstrated that, despite their lack of innate capacity to manufacture the hormone, hepatocytes can be utilized as an extra source of insulin following genetic modification. Genetically modifying the enzyme in diabetic rats has been shown to reduce blood glucose levels by 38% and raise blood insulin levels by 67%. However, it also had a significant impact on fat metabolism, raising levels of triglycerides by 190% and free fatty acids by 310%. According to those findings, genetically modifying hepatic GCK is currently not regarded as a reliable method of treating diabetes. Conversely, pdx 1 expression [169] in diabetes mouse hepatocytes has been shown to raise plasmatic insulin levels by 300%, indicating that genetic modification of this transcription factor may be taken into consideration to develop novel anti-diabetic treatments [170].

Stem cell Therapy

Stem cell therapy is one of the newest and most sophisticated methods for treating major metabolic diseases like diabetes [170-178]. Stem cells are rapidly proliferating cells that can develop into any kind of cell in the body, including muscle, pancreas, and brain cells. When nonmyeloablative hematopoietic stem cell transplantation (AHST) was utilized to treat type 1 diabetes in individuals on immunosuppressive medications, the results of stem cell therapy were assessed [178]. Over several months, patients received intravenous injections of stem cells. C peptide levels rose six months after the transplant, indicating increased insulin production. However, there was a decrease in anti-glutamic acid decarboxylases (GAD) plasmatic levels, which are typically elevated in type 1 diabetic patients and suggest immune-mediated beta cell death. Patients who no longer needed intense insulin therapy showed better beta cell activity, as evidenced by lower blood glucose levels and A HbA1c concentration below 7% [178]. Although it has been shown to improve beta cell function, stem cell transplantation is not advised for individuals with diabetic ketoacidosis. Even though stem cell therapy has been shown to be successful in reversing hyper glycaemia, most patients need insulin or traditional anti-diabetic therapy a few months after the transplant because beta cell mass decreases over time for immune system activation [175]. If the patient's stem cells are derived from the same patient rather than from donors, the immune-mediated loss of beta cells can be prevented. According to this viewpoint, the main goal of stem cell therapy is to reprogrammed diabetic patients' fibroblasts into induced pluripotent stem cells (iPS) that are intended to differentiate into beta cells, which are subsequently replanted in the patient's highly vascularized body tissues [176].

Conclusion

Diabetes mellitus is a most common endocrine disorder, which has affected millions of people in the world. It is a type of disease which is caused by hyperglycemia resulting from imperfections in insulin secretion, insulin action or both. The available drugs for the diabetes mellitus that are present have many side effects and problems like unwanted hypoglycemia that are the turning point of the research to shift towards

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3007-3189

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traditionally available medicines which have low side effect and wide range of bio activity and seems highly attractive. From this review article, it is useful for the health professionals, scholars and scientists to develop alternative medicines on the basis of available evidence to cure different kinds of diabetic problems using herbal preparations substances and extracts like *momordica charantia*, *carica papaya*, *allium sativum*, *aloe bobsdensis*, *Mangifera indica*, *Eugenia jambolana*. These plants extracts for use for the treatment of diabetes mellitus and they shows significant role in controlling hyperglycemia that are isolated from different plants plays very important role to design medicines and treat hyperglycemic problems. Studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of new classes of medications, like GLP-1 receptor agonists SGL2 inhibitors, Sulfonylureas, DPP-4 inhibitors, Biguanides, Thiazolidinediones these chemicals were used in enhancing glycemic control and lowering the cardiovascular risk. Additionally, advances insulin delivery devices and emerging trends such as artificial pancreas system and stem cell technology, hold promise for further improving diabetes management. The exact mechanisms by which LDR prevents diabetes are unknown, they may involve immunomodulation to maintain of pancreatic function and the activation of pancreatic antioxidants to shield beta cells from oxidative damage. The mechanisms underlying LIL's therapeutic effect on diabetic wound healing may include immunomodulation, cell proliferation stimulation, antioxidant action, and enhancement of systemic and wound regional microcirculation. Therefore, numerous research have shown that LDR, specifically LIL, is a therapeutically effective treatment for diabetic wound healing, even though there are only a handful that show LDR prevents the development of diabetes. These early findings are motivating for us development of diabetes. Certain other therapies like newer insulin, insulin delivery devices, islet cell transplantation, stem cell technology, artificial pancreas systems were made for glucose management. Some conventional therapeutic approaches like exercise and weight control, medical nutrient therapy, oral glucose drugs like biguanides, sulfonylureas, meglitinides and thiazolidinediones are the primary classes of oral medications used for the glucose management. Patients with type 1 diabetes who are unable to make insulin spontaneously are treated with some insulin injections which are made for the control of diabetes. Some gene therapies and stem cell therapies both in vivo and in vitro are made to replace the damaged beta cells in the pancreas, and the liver is a target organ for gene therapy. When nonmyeloablative hematopoietic stem cell transplantation was utilized to treat type 1 diabetes in individuals on immunosuppressive medications, the results of stem cell therapy were assessed. Over several months patients were received intravenous injections of stem cells. C peptide levels rose six months after the transplant, including increased increase insulin production.

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